

Law as a Drive for Social Development in Philippe Malaurie's Thinking

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ABSTRACT: The paper defines the concept of law and its role in the development of a society, in Philippe Malaurie's thinking. In this endeavour, this paper offers a historical sketch of personalities who, through their ideas on legal science, have contributed—to a lesser or a greater extent—to the harmonious development and the progress of society.

KEY WORDS: law, ethics, principles, progress, heroes

Society can be defined by the multitude of people who make it, people interconnected through social, economic and legal relationships. Due to the importance of law science in society through the legal norms it imposes upon people's conduct, it cannot be separated from the evolution of society.

Law is an aggregate of principles, concepts and legal norms that embody the fundamental conditions and moral ideals of a society and which serves a double purpose. The first one is to prevent illicit behaviours and to encourage people to a high legal and moral conduct. The second purpose is punitive, as law tries to restore the original legal order through sanctions.

As the worldwide society is composed of a multitude of nations, cultures and beliefs that we could define in one word as diversity, there was a need to build a mechanism that would regulate the relationship between these different states. This has led to the

regulation of international law that was established in “the process of collaboration and struggle between the states of the international community.”¹

International law aims to settle and resolve those conflicts that could arise due to existing domestic laws from different countries. This need has made its presence felt more and more acute with the increasing trade agreements between states, as well as with the increasing relations in areas like tourism, culture, sciences, etc.

With the ever-growing development of society, specialized international institutions have been created to ensure compliance with the legal norms and respect for the rights of states and their citizens. These institutions include the *International Court of Justice*, the *International Criminal Court*, the *European Court of Justice* and the *European Court of Human Rights*.

As we mentioned in the beginning, society is made up of people, and the progress in various areas over the centuries, is also due to them. Some of them have made impressive contributions in the evolution of law ever since it was not yet formed as an independent legal science.

At the beginning of our society there were talks about a so-called “natural law.” It consisted in a set of rules of conduct for various situations, but it was not written, but it was transmitted by word of mouth through successive generations. One of the first ones to regulate these principles was Moses. History speaks of him as “one of the greatest heroes of mankind, the founder of a religion, father of a nation, legislator, moralist, liberator, conqueror.”²

Through Moses, God gave for the first time the written law consisting of the Ten Commandments given on Mount Sinai. Thus, the Moral Law of God has always been considered the legal basis of all law systems.

Since the people of Israel were, at the time, a fairly intolerant and aggressive people, some laws are intransigent. As an example, we find the death sentence for apostasy: “If there is found among you, within any of your gates which the Lord your God gives you, a man or a woman who has been wicked in the sight of the Lord your God, in transgressing His covenant, who has gone and served other gods and worshiped them, either the sun or moon or any of

the host of heaven, which I have not commanded, and it is told you, and you hear of it, then you shall inquire diligently. And if it is indeed true and certain that such an abomination has been committed in Israel, then you shall bring out to your gates that man or woman who has committed that wicked thing, and shall stone to death that man or woman with stones" (Deut. 17:2-5).³ One also finds Lex Talionis (the law of retaliation) "Your eye shall not pity: life shall be for life, eye for eye, tooth for tooth, hand for hand, foot for foot" (Deut. 19:21).⁴

Going further, we come to the three great Greek philosophers who, through their ideas and work, have tried to impress unto the Western world a moral and intellectual basis whose presence would be felt over the centuries. Plato, in particular, along with Socrates and Aristotle, devotes much of his work to the endeavour of trying to fight against moral, social and political decadence. He thought that these degrading vices had appeared in society because his Sophist opponents had argued that everything was relative, that there was no absolute justice or absolute good, and that each individual should only relate to himself.

Another name that has left its mark on the development of society was that of Cicero. It is said that he was the greatest lawyer of his time. He was the embodiment of courage, assuming the work he wanted to do even by risking his own life. In the end he was assassinated, but for us he stayed as an example of "lawyer, humanist and martyr for freedom."⁵

A true illustrious of law and, in the same time, someone who has influenced society to this day is Justinian. In his capacity as Emperor of the Eastern Roman Empire, he wished for legal order and unity over the land he was leading. He wished for the law to be written and accessible to everyone, both to the ordinary and to the rich. This is how he began his vast work that includes: the *Digesta*, the *Institutiones*, the *Codex*, the *Novellae*, and the *Corpus*. He managed to establish only for a short time the legal unity he wished for, but his imprint transcended over the centuries, so that he accomplished what he himself declared at the end of his vast and impressive work: "For a few pennies, the poor and the rich can now buy the laws and obtain at a low price the quintessence of wisdom."⁶

Blaise Pascal proves us that society cannot progress if it only relies on one area. His connection with law is a secondary one, as he was interested in religion, philosophy and, his main interest, the human being as a whole. Pascal's complex interest only proves that, without respecting the norms, man's life and destiny cannot follow their natural course. Through his work, Pascal tried to capture the fine difference between man's grandness and man's nothingness, and to show that without God's laws there was no law and justice. "What sort of freak then is man! How novel, how monstrous, how chaotic, how paradoxical, how prodigious! Judge of all things, feeble earthworm, repository of truth, sink of doubt and error, glory and refuse of the universe! Know then, proud man, what a paradox you are to yourself. Be humble impotent reason! Be silent, feeble nature! Learn that man infinitely transcends man, hear from your master your true condition, which is unknown to you. Listen to God."⁷

France gave one of her most famous writers and philosopher of the Lumières, Voltaire. Voltaire came from a family connected with law, his father being a notary. He thus had solid knowledge in law although he never finished his law studies because, as he affirmed, school filled his mind with a lot of nothingness. Despite his statement, he remained faithful to law, and he fought for a common law all over France because, he used to say: "A man who takes the post-chaise, in France, changes laws more often than he changes horses."⁸This great thinker left his mark mainly on criminal law, which he tried to reform on the occasion of the Calas business.

His work does not present Jean-Jacques Rousseau as a man of contrasts, having a decisive influence in the French Revolution and on French constitutional law. However, he was convinced that the civil society of his time, through the laws it was passing, was destroying the State of Nature established by divinity. He strongly advocated that the right to property should not belong to each individual, but it should be a common right, a so-called "savage good" belonging to all. Voltaire, in turn, vehemently contradicted this concept of no individual goods or properties, and at some point they even had an exchange on the subject. Voltaire wrote the following as soon as he received Rousseau's book on the topic: "I have received, sir, your new book against the human species; . . . no one has ever been so

witty as you are in trying to turn us into brutes: to read your book makes one long to go on all fours. . . . I must confine myself to being a peaceful savage in the retreat I have chosen—close to your country.” Rousseau, a man full of energy, replies: “I dislike you. You have caused me offenses to which I was especially sensitive—I, your disciple and admirer. . . . Finally, I hate you for what you wanted this, but hating you, I realize that I could love you, if you so wish.”⁹

From the above, we can easily come to the idea that social progress lies in people and the ideas they bring. Even though norms and values of a scholar do not always match the thinking and understanding of another, over time, these principles and controversies have left their mark in the development of the society. Thus, society has been able to test theories and principles and to keep only those norms and discoveries it found useful.

We have reached the apogee of the Age of Enlightenment, where the concept of natural law would slowly find its end. This period was marked by the personality of a celibate philosopher, Immanuel Kant, who lived a quiet and accurate life, without too many daily events. It is said that those around him used to fix their watches according to his regular daily walks. His writings are also rigid, formal, devoid of charm and difficult to understand. However, we owe him for his profound leaning on the topics of law and morals and the link between the two, as well as for the principle of autonomy of the will. As his writings are difficult to present in common words, as they can always be interpreted in various ways, we shall quote use a quote help us notice the way he saw this link between equity and morality: “Suppose that a domestic servant is paid his wages at the end of a year in money that has depreciated in the interval, so that he cannot buy with it what he could have bought with it when he concluded the contract. The servant cannot appeal to his right to be compensated when he gets the same amount of money but it is of unequal value. He can appeal only on grounds of equity (a mute divinity that cannot be heard). . . . The motto (dictum) of equity is, «the strictest right is the greatest wrong» (*summum ius, summa iniuria*). But this ill cannot be remedied by way of what is laid down as right, even though it concerns a claim to a right; for this claim belongs only to the court conscience (*forum poli: forum*

= court, *polus* = sky, polar star), whereas every question of what is laid down as right must be brought before civil right (*forum soli; solum* = earth).¹⁰

Thanks to Kant's theory and to other philosophers and jurists, we have now the theory of imprevision, which allows changes in the contract terms or its adaptation so that it corresponds to the reality of the moment when it is performed. Are taken into account those situations when, due to major unforeseen circumstances or irreparable changes, the one who signed the contract would suffer unjust damages. It is thus desirable to eliminate the effects of inequality between the contracting parties.

The last well-known name we shall submit to a brief analysis on his contribution to law is Honoré de Balzac, who in his works insister more on private law, the law dealing with relationships between people, governing the institution of marriage, relations between neighbours, etc. We could say that this is a guiding line for society so that its people could develop in peace, freedom and harmony, freedom that exists for each individual as long as it does not limit the freedom of another.

Thus a topic that particularly draws Balzac's attention is that of marriage. He addresses the topic in many of his works, but especially in *A Marriage Contract*. He argues that the marriage institution is fundamental to society, but blames bourgeois marriages. He says that laws are not to blame for the existing abuse of power of the men in the institution of marriage and for women being invited to commit adultery. The ones to be blamed are the morals. So, he concludes, the morals of a society are the ones who should change, not its laws.¹¹

In conclusion, we could say that social progress is indissolubly linked to its people. We have presented briefly some ideas of outstanding personalities of the world over the ages, personalities who left their mark through their work and their reformist ideas and principles. Sometimes conflicting, sometimes convergent, all these ideas have nurtured our society and made it develop culturally, socially and morally.

NOTES

- ¹ Gheorghe Bobos, *Teoria Generală a Dreptului* (Cluj-Napoca: Editura Dacia, 1994), 175.
- ² Philippe Malaurie, *Antologia Gindirii Juridice* (București: Editura Humanitas, 1997), 13.
- ³ *The Holly Bible*, New King James Version.
- ⁴ *Ibid.*
- ⁵ Malaurie, 39.
- ⁶ *Ibid.*, 47.
- ⁷ *Ibid.*, 107.
- ⁸ *Ibid.*, 127.
- ⁹ *Ibid.*, 140.
- ¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 166.
- ¹¹ *Ibid.*, 207–220.